

CHILD DEVELOPMENT CENTER EDUCATIONAL NEEDS ASSESSMENT

(A Needs-Based Research of the Mother Rita Barcelo Outreach Center)

By:

Celaje, Maria Shaula R

Laniog, Lourdes, Ph.D.

September 2016

Abstract

In this study, the Mother Rita Barcelo Outreach Center (MRBOC) of La Consolacion College, Iriga City, evaluated the educational needs of the staff and students at three Child Development Centers: Divine Grace, Nightingale, and St. Francis Day Care Centers. During the academic year 2016–2017, thirty parents or guardians and three teachers were interviewed and given survey questionnaires using a descriptive study methodology. The findings showed that the daycare teachers needed a lot of help using educational technology, including online resources, and executing a variety of learning activities, including games, singing, and storytelling. According to their parents, the kids needed help with their early reading and writing skills the most, while socialization skills were only somewhat needed. Using student-assisted teaching activities that emphasized reading, storytelling, and classroom participation, an intervention program was put into place in light of the findings. The study emphasizes how crucial needs-based evaluation is when organizing educational outreach and community extension initiatives that take early childhood development into account.

Key Words: Child Development Center; Educational Needs Assessment; Community Extension; Early Childhood Education; Teacher Training

I. INTRODUCTION

La Consolacion College, Iriga City maintains the Mother Rita Barcelo Program for Outreach and Extension Services. The school has active partnership with City Social Welfare and Development Office (CSWDO). Over the years, the school through its extension program has become more involved with the agency. It is an institutional program that is dynamic, relevant and responsible to the challenge of the present times.

This program is in line with the congregation's and the school's option for the poor as well as the act of creating a harmonious school and community relations.

Statement of the Problem

This study was an attempt to assess the educational improvement needed by teachers of three Child Development centers namely: Divine Grace Day Care Center, Nightingale Day Care Center and St. Francis Day Care Center for the academic year 2016 – 2017. Similarly, it sought to determine educational improvement needed by the day care children as perceived by their parents and guardians.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the educational improvements needed by the Day Care Teachers of the three Child Development Centers?
2. What are the educational improvement needed by the day care children as perceived by their parents and guardians?
3. What educational assistance can the LCCI students offer to the Child Development Centers?

Assumption

This study has the following assumptions:

1. That the three (3) Child Development Center teachers are in need of teacher-assistants for their classes.
2. That the Day Care Children are in need of educational visual aids to assist in their studies.
3. That the LCCI students can offer educational assistance to the Child Development Centers.

Significance of the Study

The school which works for human and community development should have a close linkage and coordination with the partner/adopted community it serves. Correspondingly, it should be aware of the present situation and needs of the recipients in order to have an effective realization and fulfillment of the outreach programs, mission and apostolate beneficial to the school and to the partner agency.

Thus, a deeper understanding and assessment of the specific needs of the agency is very indispensable for this will give the school more concrete ideas which will assist its staff and students in the planning and implementation of the most effective and needed programs of the partner agency for the next development phase.

Specifically this study will benefit the:

Day Care Children. In the improvement of their socialization skills, reading and writing skills.

Day Care Teacher. An avenue to have refresher and updating of the basic facilitation of skills to learners.

College (La Consolacion College). A prospect to serve and contribute to the development of its community.

Community. A chance to have a more productive citizens contributing to future development.

Education teacher and students. An opportunity to apply all the theories learned in the classroom and for continuous search for higher learning.

Scope and Delimitation

The study was focused on the assessment of the educational needs of day care teachers and day care children of three Child Development Center under the supervision of City Social Welfare and Development Office, namely Divine Grace day Care center; Nightingale Day Care center and St. Francis Day Care Center for the academic year 2016 – 2017. The respondents of the study were delimited to three (3) teachers and (30) parents/guardian respondents who are recipients of the LCCI-MRBOC. The respondents were given the survey questionnaire administered by the outreach coordinator and six (6) education students.

Theoretical Framework

The La Consolacion College - Iriga as a higher learning institution brings to bear in its extension programs its expertise in instruction and research. The College through the Mother Rita Barcelo Outreach Center (MRBOC) envisions developing socially aware, sensitive and responsive members of the community through active involvement in community extension activities towards community development.

The extension agenda of the school has five components which include education programs, environmental advocacy programs, empowerment programs, exposure / immersion programs and Christian formation program.

Education programs refer to organized educational activities for identified needs of specific sectors or communities with the aim of improving their conditions. Environmental advocacy program is a response to the greening program of our National Government and as mitigation to Climate Change, the Living legacy: Plant a Tree, Nurture our Future Program. This is a convergence initiative of the school wherein all pupils and students including school personnel take part in tree growing activity in their own backyards. Christian formation program, as a school rooted in Gospel values are intended to guide the formation of the whole community and an inspiration to do the works of mercy to our partner communities and agencies. Empowerment Program follows Christ teaching of *“Give man a fish, and the man will live for a day, but teach a man how to fish and then he will live for a lifetime”* wherein adopted communities are being nourished not only with the word of God, but with the necessary skill to find a source of living so as to provide their basic needs and most importantly an opportunity to live a dignified life. The Exposure Program is an avenue to raise awareness among our students to the social realities of life and its dilemma. Through exposure, we aim to engage our Augustinian students to understand others who are poor, deprived, oppressed and exploited and inculcate social roles and responsibilities as part of our vision-mission.

Planning and implementing the different extension program components through the different extension services are guided by four extension principles. The extension

program should be Needs-based and guided, Core-Values oriented, ASAS mission oriented, and participatory. These principles are significant in materializing the purpose of any extension program. An extension program should stem from or at least complements an existing academic or research program relative to the assessment, analysis, and resolution of the target group's needs and concerns (needs-based and guided); transformative and more aligned to the ASAS pastoral priorities which are directed towards the poor, the marginalized, the indigenous peoples, and the youth and for environmental protection (ASAS mission oriented); and it seeks to holistically form students that are Compassionate, Gospel- Value oriented, intellectually competent and are open to growth (Core Values); also its engages all stakeholders which include the implementers and clientele (participatory). Figure 1 shows theoretical paradigm.

Figure 1 Community Extension Framework

The conduct of the school extension programs follows a process. Problems should be identified first only then that specific needs of the target group are to be assessed. The results of the needs assessment serve as the basis for extension program proposal-making. Approved extension program proposal should be processed for its implementation. Once the extension program is implemented, constant monitoring should

be ensured to finally meet the objectives of the program. The extension program will only be terminated if it has attained its purpose.

II. METHOD AND PROCEDURE

The research method used was descriptive method.

A. Subjects

The respondents of this study were 100% of the total number of teacher recipient and 33% of the parents/guardians of the enrolled day care children in Child Development Center of San Roque and San Francisco, Iriga City.

B. Instrument

The main data gathering tool used to collect data was the questionnaire.

However, to support the information gathered through the questionnaire, an informal interview was also conducted to validate the responses of the respondents on the questionnaire. Respondents were assisted and oriented well before answering the questionnaire given.

C. Administration

The outreach coordinator and education students personally administered the questionnaire and conducted interview. Respondents were assisted and oriented well before answering the questionnaire given.

D. Statistical Treatment

The data gathered by the researcher were tallied and tabulated. The statistic employed in the interpretation of the data was the weighted mean, percentage and the ranking distribution.

The responses of the survey were tabulated and assigned after computing the mean occurrence such as that:

4.50 – 5.00	Strongly Needed
3.50 – 4.49	Moderately Needed
2.50 – 3.49	Needed
1.50 – 2.49	Fairly Needed
1.49 – and below	Not Needed

III. PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF THE DATA

Needs of the Day Care Teacher

The needs assessment survey was conducted last July 22, 2016 to the Day Care Centers namely: Nightingale Day Care of San Francisco, Iriga City, Divine Day Care Center of San Roque, Iriga City and St. Francis Day Care of San Francisco, Iriga City. The survey questionnaire was administered to the teachers and parents of the children of the three Day Care centers by the Head of MRBOC with the assistance of the third year teacher education students

After administration of the survey questionnaire, the responses were tallied and weighted mean was computed for interpretation. Table shows the needs of the Day Care teachers in terms of educational improvement.

Table I Educational Improvement Needs

Needs	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Various experiences and activities such as songs, games and story-telling	4.50	Strongly Needed	1.5
2. Activities that build children's self-esteem	2.50	Needed	9
3. Speak effectively and improve oral exercises	3.00	Needed	8
4. Learn about technology and media literacy			
4.1 Microsoft Office Word	4.00	Moderately Needed	5
4.2 Microsoft Office Powerpoint	4.00	Moderately Needed	5
4.3 Microsoft Office Excel	4.00	Moderately Needed	5
4.4 Use of internet	4.50	Strongly Needed	1.5
5. Learn Visual Literacy	4.00	Moderately Needed	5
6. Learn other teaching strategies	4.00	Moderately Needed	5
Average Weighted Mean	3.83	Moderately Needed	

It could be gleaned from the table that of the nine needs of the Day Care teacher rank first were the various experiences and activities such as songs, games and story-telling, and the use of internet with a weighted mean of 4.50, respectively which means strongly needed. While the other five needs were rated 4.00 as its weighted mean which means moderately needed and the last two needs were rated 3.00 and 2.50 respectively which means needed. And the average weighted mean was 3.83 which means moderately needed. It can be inferred that all items are needed so intervention is required for the improvement of the teacher.

Needs of the Children

There were three needs cited in the survey questionnaire namely: learn socialization, assistance in beginning reading and assistance in beginning writing. The needs of the children were identified by their parent.

Of the needs rank first were assistance in beginning reading and assistance in beginning writing with weighted mean of 4.50 respectively which means strongly needed and learn socialization was rated 4.375 as its weighted mean which means moderately needed.

From this results it can be inferred that the children needs how to read and write. Actually these are are the first step in their formal education.

Moreover, the parents of the children were Catholic. It follows that their children are catholic.

Proposed Intervention

The third year teacher education students are assigned to assist the Day Care teachers on Friday starting August, 2016 to February, 2017 at least three-hours per meeting. Below is the proposed class session as the intervention.

Class Session

AM

8:00 – 8:30	Religion/Song
8:30 - 9:00	Writing
9:00 - 9:30	Games
9:30 – 10:00	Break Time
10:00 – 10:30	Reading
10:30 – 11:00	Story-Telling

PM

1:00 – 1:30	Religion/Song
1:30 – 2:00	Writing
2:00 – 2:30	Games
2:30 – 3:00	Break Time
3:00 – 3:30	Reading
3:30 – 4:00	Story-Telling

Copy of songs, games and stories will be provided to the Day Care teachers. This may assist them in their teaching-learning process.

Evaluation will be given to the children before the end of the term. This will be in a form of oral and written test. The result of this evaluation will determine the achievement of the children and the success of the intervention.